

INNOVATIVE TEACHING IN FRESHWATER ENTOMOLOGY

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Abstract

Freshwater entomology is a part of course for Post-graduation at Zoology. Instead of teaching this topic with conventional lecture and laboratory method, if it is taught with the lecture, lab, audio-visual and field visit, it would be more learning than just memorisation. This will enhance students understanding of ecology and insect species interactions.

Introduction

Freshwater entomology is one of the parts of freshwater zoology course taught at post-graduation in zoology of Pune University, Pune (Anonymous 2013). In this part, teaching of identification of freshwater insects is a necessary aspect of course. In this course university has assigned three hours of theory and two hours of laboratory session.

In this course, teacher discusses the specific adaptation in aquatic insect for their survival in aquatic habitat using lecture method. Before starting this topic in classroom lecture, teacher has to elaborate the identification characters of aquatic insect, at least for the selected examples of aquatic insect. These identification characters are hardly discussed in the laboratory setting or in previous classes of undergraduate level. But often teacher have to revise during lecture hours in addition. Here at all levels of learning, student plays a role of listeners without active participation. Student do not collect and verify this characters on their personal collections. Particularly diagnostic or adaptations characters are discussed and shown on an individual basis unless student inquires about it. In teaching freshwater insect identification, instructor relies on demonstration material maintained in laboratory museums or on personal collection or else use to show only photographs and images of insects.

Are these students of this course, expected to capture and identify a personal collection of freshwater Aquatic insects? The answer from university syllabus is 'yes'. In semester-field visit this collection is expected by student and instructor. But often the laboratory assistant or instructor brought and preserve them in laboratory museum to be used year by years. There is no any fixed method for the evaluation system or scoring or grading

system of each student's collection. The quality of the collection is evaluated by about as many different methods as there are instructors. In the syllabus, identification of freshwater insects and their adaptation is only expected. To enhance students' learning experience, teacher can organise a relevant field visit at nearby ponds, lakes or rivers to aid the classroom teaching.

Taking into consideration all above points in present study we adapted a very innovative teaching program for freshwater entomology.

Methodology

During a classroom hour, we detail the theoretical points related with the insect ecology and adaptation. Then in next laboratory hours we introduced them with identification characters of those insects showing special adaptation for aquatic life. In second half of the lecture session, showed a documentary film on aquatic insect specifically prepared and directed by German Gutierrez (2001) for Discovery channel. Then they were acquainted with museum specimens. This all efforts were focused with the intention to make them familiar with those aquatic insect identifications.

In second classroom session, students learned about morphological modification and necessity of locomotors and respiratory adaptation in aquatic insects.

Where as in next laboratory session field visit was organised at nearby pond (Khambal Lake, Meharavani, Trambak, Nashik). Where there is a rich insect diversity and aquatic ecosystem is conserved. Along with student, teacher and laboratory assistant, and all necessary equipment's like field microscope, net, dissection boxes, slides, fixative, magnifying glasses, photographic units, camera, folding table, glassware and containers, laptop with modem and active internet connection we visited the site.

Following all the necessary precautions, students are asked to look for aquatic insect which they have already observed in the museum. As they are well acquainted with some of these insects in laboratory and classroom session, they take interest in observing many more insects, their adaptations, and interactions with the other components of the ecosystem. They collect insect specimens and try to identify their own in the temporary laboratory setup on the

site. To confirm their identifications they prefer to use the provided photo-catalogues, monographs and books (Merritt et. al., 1978), even some time they take use of laptops and internet to confirm their findings. They take photograph of these insect during their active learning in the pond ecosystem. Finally they study and collect many more new specimens of aquatic insect and their life stages which they have not even seen in college museum.

Role of teachers

- To identify the site for field visit having rich aquatic ecosystem.
- To organise, control and manage the field visit and temporary lab setup at the site.
- To encourage student to explore the ecosystem for more and more species interaction observations.
- Give at hand guidance for the setting temporary laboratory near pond,
- Give quick reference for the observation and preservation technique of aquatic insects,
- To encourage the student to collect and identify new insect species
- To details about the similarities of adaptive and diagnostic characters of the insect collected by students.
- To observe the involvement of individual student in the ecosystem exploration.
- To judge the performance of each student for assigning the marks and grades.

Outcome of methodology

- This creates enthusiasm in student for learning the subject (Jaus 1977).
- Target oriented field visit fulfilled the objectives of syllabus.
- The time spends at the site by student initiated thinking and questioning about the other ecological factors and they discuss the adaptive characters of other organism.
- Accompanying reference material at site like Computer data base, internet facility, book and photo-catalogues give chance to learn many other organisms found on the site.
- It initiates group discussion and healthy transfer of peer knowledge.
- The main advantage of this exercise is that it helps the student associated some ecological concepts with an observed phenomenon.

- Also the information collected by teacher is utilised to answer other questions raise by student rather than being ignored as often happens with routine laboratory exercise (Anonymous 2003).
- This create aptitude for the research when newer, unidentified insect species and their adaptation, ecological interaction are observed by students.
- They memorise lots of event, species, and phenomenon happened during the field visit to inquire and correlate it with the classroom teaching later on.

Summery

Freshwater entomology is a part of postgraduate course in Zoology. For teaching this course in syllabus three lectures and one practical weightage is given by University. Instead of traditional teaching, if innovative field laboratory teaching method is adapted with the classroom and museum session, it will give lots of advantage to students and teachers in their learning process.

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Reference

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